

ONLINE Event – Digital Summer School 2020

Research Data Management

(Foto: [Fabian Grohs](#), [Unsplash](#))

Wednesday, 8th July 2020 at 2 p.m.

Language: German **(with English translations)**

The event is provided with the BigBlueButton **(BBB)** web conference system:

<https://bbb.uni-hildesheim.de/b/ann-avy-4ww>

Moderation: Annette Strauch, M.A. (Contact: annette.strauch@uni-hildesheim.de)

Research Data Management (RDM)

How do we improve the usability of research data to move science forward? ‘Good Practices’ and ‘Lessons Learned’ from KIT. The National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) will continue to be established so that research data can become scientifically widely usable in the sense of data treasures with social added value, also with the goal of connectivity, e.g. to the European Research Cloud (European Open Science Cloud, EOSC). The summer event is aimed at researchers from all departments and institutes of the University of Hildesheim, as well as interested parties from the global RDM community (libraries, data centers, data protection officers, etc.), as well as for all those who are interested in our topics (Citizen Science) .

‘Guest Speakers’

□ Dr. Claudia Kramer, Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT), Deputy Head Research Services (Science Management):

“Research Data Management at KIT”.

□ Director Prof. Dr. Bernhard Weisser, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin – Preußischer Kulturbesitz. Münzkabinett (Numismatic Collection),

NFDI4 Objects:

“Cross-collection collaboration in numismatics.

The Authority File Portal and new perspectives with NFDI4 Objects ”.

□ Jens Kloppmann, Charlotte Kastner (Programmfabrik):

“Building flexible research data repositories with easydb“.

Program

14:00-14:10 “Welcome” und “Kick-Off” (RDM at University of Hildesheim Foundation, RDM, University Library Hildesheim).

14:10-14:25 Presentation: “Research Data Management at KIT”.

14:25-14:35 Discussion with all.

14:35-14:50 Presentation: “Cross-collection collaboration in numismatics. The Authority File Portal and new perspectives with NFDI4 Objects ”.

14:50-15:00 Discussion with all.

15:00-15:15 Presentation: **“Building flexible research data repositories with easydb“.**

15:15-16:00 Discussion with all.

16:00 “Closing”.

Abstracts

☐ Annette Strauch

Since March 2018, the University Library's service-oriented offers have been focussing on all researchers, i.e. from the bachelors to the post-docs as well as on all employees of the university. Research data are all data that arise in the research process or are the result of it. Research results have also changed in the way they are presented today, i.e. the 'research outputs' are not only interesting and important for re-usable research in the context of scientific publications, but often when collecting data itself. Data becomes important in connection with a scientific data set or with scientific research software and various versioning systems. Research practice has therefore become an important part of research, for example how to use the research tools, how to deal with methods and, in general, the question within a project, what research actually means project-specifically, and how research is organized in every project.

☐ Dr. Claudia Kramer

"Pure data acquisition does not bring science any further. The key is to improve the availability and reusability of research data."

Under this motto, a team of IT specialists, librarians, scientists and other experts at KIT work together in the service team RDM, and to support researchers in all stages of the research process in FAIR data management. The offers include, for example, the Research Data Management Organizer RDMO tool, the directory for repositories re3data, and the information platform forschungsdaten.info. In addition to support local projects at KIT, the service team is also a partner in the development of RDM structures in the country (e-science initiative, nationwide (NFDI) and EOSC in a global context. It is always about the development of use cases and the establishment of best practice examples of how „responsible“ research can succeed in the context of good scientific practice.

□ Prof. Dr. Bernhard Weisser

The database work for the Münzkabinett, Numismatic Collection (State Museums in Berlin) has gained a new quality in 2017. Funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, the Münzkabinett is participating in a project to develop coins in 40 participating university collections. The results are presented on a separate project website: www.numid-verbund.de. Within this network, the Münzkabinett as a non-university partner has three tasks: It is responsible for the processing and export of the required standard data enriched with IDs / LOD to the project partners. A separate portal was activated for this in 2019: <https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp>. The Münzkabinett coordinates the export of data from all IKMK partners, for which the formats LIDO and since 2019 JSON are available, and it offers advice and assistance with object documentation. Since 2019, all numismatic digitization projects have been involved in the application process to create a national research data infrastructure and focus there on the NFDI4objects consortium <https://www.nfdi4objects.net>.

□ Jens Kloppmann, Charlotte Kastner (Programmfabrik)

easydb is a flexible web framework to build up any kind of object, metadata and media repositories and to manage research data. easydb is offered at many university libraries as a central service to map different data structures in one or more instances. The focus is less on dynamic publishing with easydb, but rather on the ingest process and the sustainable management of metadata and related files. Based on the FAIR criteria, easydb features such as indexing and search, authentication and rights management, relational data structure, norm data support or DOI allocation will be part of the presentation and clarified with selected reference projects.

Sie wurden zur Teilnahme eingeladen

Digital Summer School 2020 - Forschungsdatenmanagement am 08.07.2020 - "Love your data!"

A Annette Strauch (Initiator)

Unter den NACHRICHTEN befinden sich die NOTIZEN. Dort befindet sich ein für alle Teilnehmenden nutzbares Feld für Geteilte Notizen. Während der Konferenz können diese Notizen jederzeit als HTML- und txt-Datei exportiert werden. Nach dem Beenden einer Konferenz werden auch die Geteilten Notizen automatisch gelöscht. Ist die Leiste der Geteilten Notizen bei Ihnen nicht geöffnet, so können Sie anhand eines roten Symbols daneben erkennen, ob gerade jemand aktiv die Notizen bearbeitet.

<https://wp.uni-oldenburg.de/edidactics/wp-content/uploads/sites/143/2020/03/BBB-Anleitung-3.0.pdf>

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Es handelt sich um einen kollaborativen Texteditor, in dem jede Person (alle Rollen) schreiben und auch kleine Formatierungen vornehmen kann.

Der Editor eignet sich zum Sammeln und Beantworten inhaltlicher Fragen, kollaboratives Lösen von Aufgaben, schriftlichen Diskurs, kollaborative Textproduktion, Protokollierung u.a.

<https://www.uni-hildesheim.de/bbb-webkonferenzen/>

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